

Controlled Ring Opening Metathesis Polymerization of a New Monomer: On Switching the Solvent -- Water-soluble Homopolymers to Degradable Copolymers

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Abstract

A new heterocyclic monomer was developed via simple Diels-Alder reaction which is reluctant to polymerize in dichloromethane (DCM) whereas undergoes facile polymerization in tetrahydrofuran (THF) with excellent control over molecular weight (M_n) and dispersities (\mathcal{D}) using Grubbs' third generation catalyst (G3). The deprotection of the *tert*-butoxycarbonyl group (BOC group) from the polymeric backbone yielded a water-soluble ROMP polymer easily. Moreover, in DCM this new monomer copolymerizes with 2,3-dihydrofuran (DHF) under catalytic living ROMP conditions to give backbone degradable polymers. All the synthesized polymers were characterized by SEC and NMR spectroscopy. We believe that this new route to water soluble ROMP homopolymers as well as the cost-effective and environmentally friendly route to degradable copolymers and block-copolymers could find applications in biomedicine in the near future.

1. Introduction

Over the past decades, water-soluble polymers have attracted the interest of the polymer community because of their numerous applications in a variety of fields such as drug delivery, sensor applications, biomaterials, flocculants, dispersants and many others. ^[1-4] Among many polymerization techniques, ring opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP) became a very versatile and attractive tool for the synthesis of water-soluble polymers because of its living

nature, high functional group tolerance, mild reaction conditions and ability to synthesize different block copolymers.^[5-14] The Schrock and Grubbs groups have successfully developed complexes based on molybdenum and ruthenium, which serve as highly effective catalysts in metathesis reactions and have gained significant applications in polymer chemistry.^[15] Out of these catalysts, the third-generation Grubbs' catalyst (G3) has emerged as the preferred choice for ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP) due to its wide availability in the commercial market and its excellent ratio of initiation to propagation rates.^[16-17]

Although, ROMP is a very attractive platform for the synthesis of water-soluble polymers there are not many monomers in the literature which can make water soluble ROMP polymers. So, it would be very interesting and important to synthesize new monomers capable of producing water-soluble polymers under living ROMP condition. The chemical functionalities along the polymer backbone are largely responsible for the water solubility. One particularly interesting functional group that imparts water solubility is the amino group. This group is found within naturally occurring water-soluble polymers, including proteins and polysaccharides. It is also present in synthetic water-soluble polymers such as poly (amino acids), poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimers, and poly(ethyleneimine).^[18-19] As amino groups impart water solubility in several natural as well as synthetic water-soluble polymers, here, we studied the controlled ROMP of a new protected amine containing monomer (synthesized via the Diels-Alder reaction of cyclopentadiene and di-*tert*-butyl azodicarboxylate),^[20] deprotection of which after polymerization yielded the water-soluble polymer in a straightforward approach.

Although the monomer M1 is reluctant to homopolymerize in DCM, it undergoes a controlled polymerization in THF. We further investigated this feature to study the copolymerization behaviour of M1 with DHF in DCM as the solvent. We had previously observed that bulky monomers which are inert towards homopolymerization could still undergo copolymerization with a sterically less demanding comonomer.^[21] Based on this knowledge, we report here a one-pot synthesis of narrowly dispersed degradable copolymers using vinyl ethers as chain transfer agents under catalytic living ROMP conditions.^[22-25] Although ROMP is one of the most efficient techniques to synthesize a wide variety of structurally and functionally diverse polymer, one of the drawbacks of the conventional living ROMP is that it requires a stoichiometric amount of ruthenium initiator with respect to the polymer chains formed. This often leads to high catalyst loadings, which is quite expensive, as well as difficult as far as removing the toxic metal contaminants from the synthesized polymers is concerned, rendering the process unattractive for industrial and biomedical applications. Thus, there has been an interest in the discovery of non-metal alternatives for ROMP. The Boydston and the Lambert

group have developed metal-free variants for ROMP to address these problems.^[26-28] Another approach for synthesizing ROMP polymers with reduced catalyst loadings is the catalytic living ROMP.^[22] Recently our group has reported a strategy for the one-pot synthesis of living and degradable ROMP polymers by copolymerizing 2,3-dihydrofuran (DHF) with several norbornene derivatives using vinyl ethers as chain transfer agents under catalytic living ROMP conditions.^[25] In that report, the ultrafast and regioselective metathesis activity of vinyl ethers was also exploited to synthesize a PEG-ROMP diblock copolymer using a PEG-based macro chain transfer agent. Here also, we have successfully shown that this new monomer can be easily copolymerized with DHF under catalytic living ROMP condition, as well as a PEG-based macro chain transfer agent was also used to synthesize a PEG-ROMP diblock copolymer with controlled dispersity and molecular weight.

Figure 1.: Structures of the catalysts, monomers, chain transfer agent and macro-chain transfer agent used in this report.

2. Results and Discussion

The monomer (M1) was synthesized quite easily via the Diels-Alder reaction of cyclopentadiene and commercially available di-*tert*-butyl azodicarboxylate in a quantitative yield^[20] (Figure 2A). Then, we first investigated the homopolymerization of monomer M1 in

DCM with Grubbs' third generation catalyst (G3). A control ^1H NMR experiment was performed using a mixture of M1 (30 equiv.) and G3 (1 equiv.) in presence of an internal standard in dichloromethane- d_2 . The addition of G3 immediately turned the solution deep blue (SI, Fig S44) but after 24 h at rt only 10 % conversion of M1 could be observed. We believe that the coordination of ruthenium to the carbonyl oxygen of the BOC group is responsible for the hindered propagation of M1. Due to increased steric bulk, the resulting carbene complex cannot further propagate, resulting in poor monomer conversion in a non-coordinating solvent like DCM. When a weakly coordinating solvent such as THF was used instead of DCM, a huge enhancement of monomer conversion ($> 97\%$ in 24 h) was achieved (SI, Fig S41, S43). Previous literature reports have also demonstrated a substantial increase in the conversion of certain ROMP monomers when transitioning the polymerization condition from noncoordinating solvents, such as DCM, to weakly coordinating solvents, such as THF [29] We next performed a series of polymerization reactions varying the monomer to G3 ratio in THF. In all cases, SEC analyses (chloroform) confirmed the excellent control over molecular weight and dispersities (P1: $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 9.31$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.11$; P2 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 15.33$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.13$; P3 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 21.04$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.12$; P4 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 27.14$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.11$) (Figure 2A,2B,2C). Furthermore, with the sequential polymerization of *exo-N*-ethylhexylborneneimide (M3) (20 equiv) followed by 70 equiv of monomer M1, a block copolymer could be synthesized. SEC measurements (first block: $M_{n,SEC}(\text{THF}) = 6.23$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.18$, diblock P5 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{THF}) = 21.78$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.29$) revealed the successful formation of a diblock copolymer P5 (SI, Fig S1, S27).

Moreover, we removed the BOC group from the polymer backbone (P1) by treating it with HCl in isopropanol to give the water-soluble polymer P1' (SI, Fig S28). P1' represents a new type of water-soluble ROMP polymer that does not rely on water-soluble side chains. Contrary to other water-soluble ROMP backbones, here, the high water solubility is provided by pyrazolidine rings which are part of the backbone structure.

Figure 2. (A.) Synthesis and polymerization of the monomer **M1** (B.) Plot of the number average molecular weight ($M_{n,SEC}$ ($CHCl_3$)) and molecular weight dispersity (D) versus monomer to initiator ratio showing a linear correlation. **G3** and monomer **M1** were employed for this polymerization. (C.) SEC ($CHCl_3$) traces of products from ROMP of monomer **M1** at varying [Monomer]: [Initiator] ratios.

Table 1. Polymerization Data of monomer M1 (P1-P4) ^[a]

Entry	Polymer	G3:Monomer (M1)	M_n (theo; kDa)	M_n (obs.) SEC ($CHCl_3$; kDa)	Dispersity D
1	P1	1:30	8.88	9.31	1.11
2	P2	1:50	14.80	15.33	1.13
3	P3	1:70	20.72	21.04	1.12
4	P4	1:90	26.64	27.14	1.11

^[a]All of the reactions were carried out in degassed THF at room temperature.

As we hypothesized that monomer M1 could copolymerize with a less bulky comonomer in DCM, we next studied the potential of M1 towards copolymerization with DHF under catalytic living ROMP conditions. ^[25] Our group has recently described a mechanism for catalytic living

ROMP^[25] exploring the ultrafast and regioselective metathesis activity of vinyl ethers.^[30-31]

There, we showed that several norbornene derivatives which are less prone to be ring-opened by a Ru- Fischer carbene copolymerize efficiently with DHF in one pot to give living as well as degradable metathesis polymers using sub stoichiometric amounts of Grubbs catalyst.

In a catalytic process the initiation kinetics of the ruthenium complex are less important than in a living polymerization. We, therefore, chose Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst (G2) which is less expensive and more bench stable for the next experiments.

To begin with, a one pot copolymerization of M1 and DHF was performed in DCM using a ratio of G2:CTA1:M1:DHF = 1:10:600:1200.^[32] A ¹H NMR measurement showed > 95 % conversion of monomer M1 in 24 h. SEC analysis of the synthesized polymer (P6: $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 20.89 \text{ kDa}$, $\text{Đ} = 1.36$) revealed a good control over molecular weight and dispersity (SI, Fig S12). As previously discussed in the earlier report,^[25] norborneneimide derivatives exhibit slow ring-opening kinetics when reacting with the propagating Ru Fischer-carbene. This characteristic facilitates a rapid and regioselective exchange between the propagating Fischer-carbene and the vinyl ether of CTA1 under the given conditions. Once all CTA1 molecules have been transferred to the polymer chain ends, the degenerative, reversible, and regioselective Fischer-carbene exchange between the end groups occurs at a faster rate than monomer propagation. This phenomenon creates the macroscopic impression that all chains are growing simultaneously. As a result, the quasi-simultaneous growth of all chains enables the straightforward synthesis of copolymers in a single reaction vessel, while maintaining control over the molecular weight (dictated by the monomer/CTA1 ratio) and achieving narrow molecular weight distributions. (Fig 3A, 3B).

Figure 3. (A) Proposed mechanism of catalytic living ROMP for the syntheses of different block copolymers using vinyl ethers as macro-chain transfer agents. (B) Mechanism of catalytic living ROMP illustrating reversible degenerative exchange between Fischer-carbene end groups.

After that a series of copolymers (P7: $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 14.42$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.34$; P8 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 5.53$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.23$; P9 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 4.16$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.21$; P10 : $M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 5.58$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.24$) were synthesized by changing the M1:CTA1 ratio and characterized by SEC and ^1H NMR spectroscopy. A linear correlation was observed as expected for a living polymerization (Fig 4A). Next, a block copolymer was synthesized via redissolving polymer P8 in DCM along with M2, DHF, and a catalytic amount of G2 to further prove the living character of the polymerization. SEC analysis showed a complete shift of the first block to give the diblock copolymer P11 ($M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 17.73$ kDa, $\mathcal{D} = 1.38$) (Fig 4B). Besides, DOSY NMR spectroscopy further confirmed the potential of the di-block copolymer formation (SI, Fig S5).

Figure 4. (A.) Plot of the number average molecular weight ($M_{n,SEC}$ (CHCl_3)) and molecular weight dispersity (Đ) versus the $[\text{M1}]/[\text{CTA1}]$ ratio showing a linear correlation. The ratios reported in brackets (z) denote the $[\text{G2}]/[\text{CTA1}]$ ratio. (B.) SEC (CHCl_3) traces of the polymer **P8** (blue) and the diblock copolymer **P11** (red).

Table 2: One-pot Catalytic Living Copolymerization Data of Monomers M1 with 2,3-DHF using chain transfer agent CTA1^[a]

Entry	Polymer	G2:CTA1:M1:DHF	M_n (Non catalytic) (kDa) ^[b]	M_n (catalytic, monomer/CTA) (theo; kDa)	M_n (obs.) (CHCl_3 ; kDa)	Đ
1	P6	1:10:600:1200	219.60	21.96	20.89	1.36
2	P7	1:15:600:1200	219.60	14.64	14.42	1.34
3	P8	1:40:600:1200	219.60	5.49	5.53	1.23
4	P9	1:60:600:1200	219.60	3.66	4.16	1.21
5	P10	1:150:2250:4500	823.50	5.49	5.58	1.24

^[a] All of the reactions were carried out in degassed DCM at room temperature.

^[b] M_n (Non catalytic) = $[\text{M1}]/[\text{G2}]$ is the maximum theoretical molecular weight under non-catalytic conditions.

After that, the high metathesis activity of vinyl ethers was exploited to synthesize a PEG-ROMP diblock copolymer using a PEG-vinyl ether-based macro chain transfer agent (m-CTA).^[33] Similarly, as described above, a PEG-based diblock copolymer P12 was synthesized via a one pot copolymerization of M1 and DHF using m-CTA under catalytic living ROMP conditions.

A clear shift in the SEC elugram for P12 ($M_{n,SEC}(\text{CHCl}_3) = 17.41 \text{ kDa}$, $\bar{D} = 1.39$) along with a single diffusing species in the DOSY NMR spectrum revealed the successful synthesis of the block copolymer. (SI, Fig S6, Fig S7)

One important feature of these copolymers is that they contain acid labile vinyl ether motifs along their backbone.^[34] As a result these polymers can easily be degraded on treatment with dilute HCl. (SI, Fig S3)

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have successfully synthesized a new amine containing monomer for the ring opening metathesis polymerization. A straightforward Diels-Alder reaction leads to this new ROMP monomer that can either form water soluble homopolymers or degradable copolymers with DHF. The polymerizations were shown to afford homopolymers in THF with controlled molecular weight, narrow dispersities and a linear relationship between the molecular weight and monomer / initiator ratio. Moreover, deprotection of the BOC group yielded a water-soluble ROMP polymer. Although this new monomer is inert towards polymerization in non-coordinating solvents like DCM, it undergoes successful copolymerization with DHF in DCM to yield degradable and living copolymers using catalytic amounts of Ru complex (up to 150 times less Ru complex than in a classical living polymerization). Apart from ROMP-ROMP diblock copolymers, a PEG-based macro chain transfer agent was also used to synthesize a PEG-ROMP diblock copolymer under catalytic living ROMP conditions. We believe that the new types of polymers presented here could be exploited as attractive building blocks for soft material applications, preparation of well-defined architectures, biomedical applications, and many others.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author upon request.

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Controlled Ring Opening Metathesis Polymerization of a New Monomer: On Switching the Solvent -- Water-soluble Homopolymers to Degradable Copolymers

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A simple Diels–Alder reaction leads to a new heterocyclic monomer for ring opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP). The new monomer is reluctant to polymerize in DCM but undergoes facile polymerization in THF to give water soluble ROMP polymers. On the other hand, it undergoes copolymerization with DHF in DCM to yield degradable polymers following a catalytic living ROMP mechanism.